

THE BASIC PROBLEMS OF TRANSLATION

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Abstract. *The aim of professional translation is to acquaint the reader with the original work of fiction; educational translation as a linguistic subject at the special institute and at school is one of the methods of more conscious and profound study of the foreign language by the way of showing up in the English text lexical, grammar and stylistic peculiarities of the English language. Before speaking of the basic principles of translating process the concept of the term “faithfulness of translation” should be determined.*

Key words: *translation, lexical meaning, synonyms, international words, neologisms, antonymic translation.*

ОСНОВНЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ ПЕРЕВОДА

Аннотация. *Цель профессионального перевода – познакомить читателя с оригинальным художественным произведением; Учебный перевод как лингвистический предмет в специальном институте и в школе является одним из методов более осознанного и углубленного изучения иностранного языка путем выявления в английском тексте лексических, грамматических и стилистических особенностей английского языка. Прежде чем говорить об основных принципах переводческого процесса, следует определить понятие термина «правдивость перевода».*

Ключевые слова: *перевод, лексическое значение, синонимы, международные слова, неологизмы, антонимический перевод.*

The difference between educational and professional translation is as follows:

The translation is considered to be faithful when the content of the book, its stylistic peculiarities are rendered by the linguistic means of the native language. It means that very often we have to use such linguistic categories of the native language, which formally don't coincide with those of the English language but have the same emotional and psychological effect on the Russian reader.

The process of educational translation presents 4 stages:

First of all the text should be thoroughly understood. It means that the student should be acquainted with the whole book, should have some knowledge of the history of literature and mode of life of the people from whose language the translation is being done. The student should realize the stylistic functions of lexical and grammar and phonetic phenomena which are used to express the content of the text. Then the work on the choice of corresponding means of expression in the native language should be done.

The last stage is a work on the Russian or Uzbek text.

The choice of the word is one of the most difficult problems of translation, which is closely connected with the following problems.

THE LOGICAL MEANING OF THE WORD.

Any grammatical phenomena or stylistic peculiarities do not always coincide with those of the foreign language as well as the meaning of these parate words, which are lexical equivalents. The main meaning of the English word “table” coincides with that of the Russian language. But the Russian “стол” has one additional meaning: “питание” “пансион” means while in English we have the special words to express the idea: “board”, “roomandboard”. At same time English “table” has the additional meaningto “таблица”. Table стол board таблица питание roomandboard пансион

INDEPENDENT AND CONNECTED MEANING OF WORD.

The logical meaning of the word maybe both independent and connected with other words. The latter can be understood in the given combination of words.

A color bar - цветной /ярко окрашенный/ барьер was seen in the distance.

There exist a color bar (расовая дискриминация) in the South Africa.

EMOTIVE MEANING OF THE WORD

A lot of words may acquire emotive meaning and the same word in different sentences maybe rendered by different words.

China is a large country (страна)

We are ready to die for our country(родина)

While translating one should take into consideration on that in different languages the words which are lexical equivalent smatteries quite different associations.

For Russians “зима” means snow and frost, for Englishmen – fog and cold wind.

“Она ходит павой перед ним”- Дело Артамоновых.

For Russians “пава” arouses the idea of something beautiful, stately, majestic, proud /а сама - то величава, выступает будто павая -Пушкин /.

For Englishmen “peahen” has nothing incommon with the sea sociations. That’s why it’s quite correct to translate the sentence as followes:

“She poses proudly before him / to pose - позировать/

THE MEANING OF THE WORD AND ITS USE.

The meaning of the word shouldn’t be mixed with its use. Sometimes even a monosemantic word canbe combined with a lot of words and is rendered in Russian by different words:

A young man- Молодой человек

A young child- Маленький ребёнок

Young in a crime- Неопытный преступник

The night is young - Началась ночь

Department of justice- Министерство юстиции

Ministry of defense- Министерство Обороны

Board of trade- Министерство торговли

Admiralty- Морское министерство

the first Lord of Admiralty- Военно- Морской министр

Chancellor -Министр финансов

War office- Военное Министерство

A bad headache - Сильная головная боль

A bad mistake- Грубая ошибка
A bad weather- Плохая погода
A bad debt -Невозвращённый долг
A bad accident- Тяжёлый / несчастный/ случай
A bad wound -Тяжёлая рана

CONTEXT

The word in the sentence may acquire so-called contextual meaning. It may be not constant, as a rule we can't find the contextual meaning of the word in the dictionary. But it always has something in common with the main meaning of the word.

“In the atomic war common and children will be first hostage.” The dictionary gives only one meaning of the given word “заложник”, but in the given sentence the word acquires a new meaning: “жертва”. It's a great difficulty to find out the contextual meaning of the word as the dictionary only gives hint show to search for the necessary word in our native town language.

The majority of the words are known to be polysemantic and the context becomes especially important while translating polysemantic words as translating in different languages is quite different.

While translating one should remember hemay use the words not included in the dictionary because it's impossible to include in the dictionary all the correct meanings of the word, which it may acquire in the context.

“He was developing grammatical nerves” - У него развивалось грамматическое чутьё.

We can find a lot of meanings of the word “nerves” “нервы, сила, мужество, хладнокровие, дерзость, нахалство” but in our text It is rendered as “чутьё”.

The student are to make out that thoughts, reflections should be translated not by separate words. So it's quite possible and natural either to introduce some words and even:

I lit my candle at the watchman's/ Dickens/-И зажёл свою свечу от фонаря ночного сторожа.

Sentences or omit them if one can manage without them.

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